

App Assessment Guidelines - Template

The following guide aims to help structure the assessment and analysis of apps and also to support teachers in selecting suitable mathematics apps. A scientific basis for the guide is provided in German language at the following source: Larkin, K., Kortenkamp, U., Ladell, S., & Etzold, H. (2019). Using the ACAT Framework to Evaluate the Design of Two Geometry Apps: An Exploratory Study. *Digital Experiences in Mathematics Education*, 5(1), 59-92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40751-018-0045-4>

Question	Note	Possible Sources
Mathematical Content Related Orientation		
What is the mathematical subject of the app?	Multiple mathematical subjects may well be possible in the app. As each subject may lead to a different area of focus, it is likely that multiple assessments of the app will be required.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • title and description of the app • supplementary materials for the app (e.g. worksheets) • external references (e.g. recommendations by others) • exploring and testing the app on your own
Our (Inter-)Actions Influence the Way We Learning		
How do students interact with specific mathematical content using the app?	<p>To answer this question, two directions need to be analyzed:</p> <p>Knowledge determines tool use Which concepts do the students have of the mathematical content? How do these influence the use of the app?</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <pre> graph LR Student((Student)) --> App((App)) App --> Student </pre> </div> <p>Tool use influences learning What are the implications of these possibilities and limitations in terms of the mathematical content of the app?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • self-directed, systematic use of the app
Does the app and its functions accurately reflect the mathematical content?	<p>Here, findings from subject didactics, subject science and psychology are used.</p> <p>In particular, it should be investigated whether the interactions analyzed in the previous step, support ideas, experiences, and competencies that are desirable or needed in mathematics education.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • synthesis of previous discussions • scientific references and publications
Learning Always Takes Place in a Social Context		
How may the app be used in a classroom setting?	<p>Possible questions include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the app useful for individual work, partner work, or work in small groups? • What are possible tasks and assignments that you can provide as a teacher? • Which differentiation methods and levels of difficulty are possible? • Is the app used for practice or does it serve to introduce new content to learners and establish basic concepts? • Does the app follow more of an instructional (e.g., drill-and-practice) or a constructivist (e.g., exploratory learning) paradigm? • What are the requirements/competencies for students to use the app? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • materials for teachers • experiments in class • fantasy

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App utilized:

What is the mathematical subject of the app?

How do students interact with specific mathematical content when using the app? Does the app accurately represent the mathematical content?

How can the app be implemented into the mathematics classroom?

possible classroom format (pairs, groups, etc.):

requirements of the students

possible differentiation methods:

possible tasks and assignments:

other ideas: